

ON VARIOUS ALMOST IDEALS OF SEMIRINGS

M. PALANIKUMAR* AND K. ARULMOZHI

ABSTRACT. In this paper, we study various almost ideals (shortly \mathcal{A} -ideals), quasi \mathcal{A} -ideals, bi quasi \mathcal{A} -ideals, tri \mathcal{A} -ideals and tri quasi \mathcal{A} -ideals in semiring and give some characterizations. Some relevant counter examples are also indicated. We develop the implications ideal \implies quasi ideal \implies bi quasi ideal \implies tri quasi ideal \implies tri quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal \implies bi quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal \implies bi \mathcal{A} -ideal \implies quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal \implies \mathcal{A} -ideal and reverse implications do not holds with examples. We show that the union of \mathcal{A} -ideals (bi \mathcal{A} -ideals, quasi \mathcal{A} -ideals, bi quasi \mathcal{A} -ideals) is a \mathcal{A} -ideal (bi \mathcal{A} -ideal, quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal, bi quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal) in semiring.

1. INTRODUCTION

Vandiver introduced the idea of semirings as a generalization of rings [19]. The notion of quasi ideal was introduced by Otto Steinfeld both in semigroups and rings [18]. Shabir et al [17] characterized the semirings by the properties of quasi-ideals. Quasi-ideals of different classes of semirings have been characterized by many authors in [2, 5]. The notion of bi-ideals in semigroups introduced by Lajos [6]. The concept of a bi-ideal is a very interesting and important thing in semiring. Bi ideal is a generalization of left ideal and right ideal. Many mathematicians proved important results and characterizations of algebraic structures by using various ideals. Rao introduced bi-quasi-ideals of semigroups. The notion of tri-ideal is a generalization of quasi ideal, bi-ideal, ideal and properties of tri ideals of a semiring [11]. Grosek and Satko introduced the notion of \mathcal{A} -ideal of semigroup [4]. In this paper, we give some properties of various \mathcal{A} -ideals in semiring. Our aim in this paper is threefold.

- (1) To study the relationship between quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal and bi quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal in a semiring.
- (2) To characterize tri \mathcal{A} -ideal in a semiring.
- (3) To characterize bi quasi ideal and tri quasi ideal in a semiring.

2. PRELIMINARIES

Definition 2.1. A non-empty subset I of a semiring $(S, +, \cdot)$ is called a subsemiring of S if $i_1 + i_2 \in I$ and $i_1 \cdot i_2 \in I$, for all $i_1, i_2 \in I$.

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*Corresponding author.

Definition 2.2. Suppose that I, B and Q are non-empty subsets of a semiring $(S, +, \cdot)$.

Then

- (i) I is called a right (left) ideal of S if I is a subsemiring of S and $IS \subseteq I$ (respectively $SI \subseteq I$). If I is a right and left ideal of S , then I is called an ideal of S .
- (ii) A subsemiring B of S is called a bi ideal if $BSB \subseteq B$.
- (iii) A subsemiring Q of S is called a quasi ideal if $QS \cap SQ \subseteq Q$.

Definition 2.3. [11] Suppose that I and Q are non-empty subsets of a semiring $(S, +, \cdot)$.

Then

- (i) I is called a right (left) tri ideal of S if $I^2SI \subseteq I(ISI^2 \subseteq I)$.
- (ii) I is called a tri ideal of S if I is a right tri ideal and left tri ideal of S .
- (iii) Q is called a right (left) bi quasi ideal if Q is a subsemigroup of S and $QS \cap QSQ \subseteq Q(SQ \cap QSQ \subseteq Q)$.
- (iv) Q is called a bi quasi ideal of S if Q is a left bi quasi ideal and right bi quasi ideal of S .

Definition 2.4. [4] Suppose that I is a non-empty subset of a semigroup S . Then

- (i) I is called a right (left) \mathcal{A} -ideal of S if $IS \cap I \neq \phi$ ($SI \cap I \neq \phi$).
- (ii) I is called a \mathcal{A} -ideal of S if I is a right \mathcal{A} -ideal and left \mathcal{A} -ideal of S .
- (iii) A subsemigroup B of S is called a bi \mathcal{A} -ideal if $BSB \cap B \neq \phi$.
- (iv) A non-empty subset Q of S is called a quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal if $[QS \cap SQ] \cap Q \neq \phi$.

3. VARIOUS \mathcal{A} -IDEALS

Here S stands for semiring unless otherwise mentioned.

Definition 3.1. Suppose that I, B and Q are non-empty subsets of a semiring $(S, +, \cdot)$.

Then

- (i) I is called a right (left) \mathcal{A} -ideal of S if I is a subsemiring of S and $IS \cap I \neq \phi$ ($SI \cap I \neq \phi$).
- (ii) I is called a \mathcal{A} -ideal of S if I is a right \mathcal{A} -ideal and left \mathcal{A} -ideal of S .
- (iii) A subsemiring B of S is called a bi \mathcal{A} -ideal if $BSB \cap B \neq \phi$.
- (iv) A subsemiring Q of S is called a quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal if $[QS \cap SQ] \cap Q \neq \phi$.

Definition 3.2. Suppose that Q is a non-empty subset of a semiring $(S, +, \cdot)$. Then

- (i) Q is called a right (left) bi quasi ideal of S if Q is a subsemiring of S and $QS \cap QSQ \subseteq Q(SQ \cap QSQ \subseteq Q)$.
- (ii) Q is called a bi quasi ideal of S if Q is a left bi quasi ideal and right bi quasi ideal of S .

Definition 3.3. Suppose that Q is a non-empty subset of a semiring $(S, +, \cdot)$. Then

- (i) Q is called a right (left) bi quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal of S if Q is a subsemiring of S and $[QS \cap QSQ] \cap Q \neq \phi$ ($[SQ \cap QSQ] \cap Q \neq \phi$).
- (ii) Q is called a bi quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal of S if Q is a left bi quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal and right bi quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal of S .

Theorem 3.1. Every ideal (bi ideal, quasi ideal) is a \mathcal{A} -ideal (bi \mathcal{A} -ideal, quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal).

Proof. Suppose that I is an ideal of S , then I is a subsemiring of S and $IS \subseteq I$ and $SI \subseteq I$. Now, $IS \cap I \subseteq I \cap I \neq \phi$ and $SI \cap I \subseteq I \cap I \neq \phi$. Hence I is a \mathcal{A} -ideal of S .

Converse of the Theorem 3.1 may not be true by the following counter Example.

Example 3.4. (i) The semiring $S_1 = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} \mid a, b, c, d \in \mathbb{Z}_2 \right\}$ and

$I = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \right\}$. Clearly I is a subsemiring and \mathcal{A} -ideal of S_1 but I is not an

ideal of S_1 by $IS_1 = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \right\} \not\subseteq I$ and

$S_1I = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \right\} \not\subseteq I$.

Let $Q = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \right\}$ is a quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal but Q is not a quasi ideal of S_1 by $QS_1 \cap S_1Q = S_1 \cap S_1 = S_1 \not\subseteq Q$.

(ii) The semiring $S_2 = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & r_1 & r_2 & r_3 & r_4 & r_5 \\ 0 & 0 & r_6 & r_7 & r_8 & r_9 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & r_{10} & r_{11} & r_{12} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & r_{13} & r_{14} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & r_{15} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \mid r_i^s \text{ are real numbers} \right\}$.

Clearly $B = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & b_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & b_2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & b_3 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \mid b_i^s \text{ are real numbers} \right\}$ is a bi \mathcal{A} -ideal of S_2 , but B

is not a bi ideal of S_2 . Since the arbitrary element $b = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \in B$ and $r =$

$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \in S_2$ such that $brb \notin B$.

Theorem 3.2. Every quasi ideal (bi ideal) is a bi quasi ideal.

Proof. Suppose that Q is a quasi ideal of S , then $QS \cap SQ \subseteq Q$. Now, $QS \cap QSQ \subseteq QS \cap SQ \subseteq Q$ and $SQ \cap QSQ \subseteq SQ \cap QS \subseteq Q$. Hence Q is a bi quasi ideal of S .

Converse of the Theorem 3.2 is not true by the following Example.

Example 3.5. In Example 3.4, the semiring S_2 is not regular by $a = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \in S_2$

there is no $x \in S_2$ such that $a = axa$.

Let $Q = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & x_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & x_2 & 0 & x_3 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \mid x_i^s \text{ are real numbers} \right\}$ is a subsemiring of S_2 .

Now, $QS_2 = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & y_1 & y_2 & y_3 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & y_4 & y_5 & y_6 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \mid y_i^s \text{ are real numbers} \right\}$ and

$S_2Q = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & z_1 & 0 & z_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \mid z_i^s \text{ are real numbers} \right\}$.

Thus, $S_2Q \cap QS_2Q \subseteq Q$ and $QS_2 \cap QS_2Q \subseteq Q$. Hence, Q is a bi quasi ideal but Q is

not a quasi ideal of S_2 by $QS_2 \cap S_2Q = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & u & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \mid u \text{ is a real numbers} \right\} \not\subseteq Q$

Corollary 3.3. *Every bi quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal is a quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal.*

Proof. Suppose that Q is a bi quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal of S , then $Q^2 \subseteq Q$ and $[QS \cap QSQ] \cap Q \neq \phi$ and $[SQ \cap QSQ] \cap Q \neq \phi$. Now, $\phi \neq [QS \cap QSQ] \cap Q \subseteq QS \cap Q$ and $\phi \neq [SQ \cap QSQ] \cap Q \subseteq SQ \cap Q$. Thus, $\phi \neq [QS \cap QSQ] \cap Q \subseteq [QS \cap SQ] \cap Q$. Hence Q is a quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal of S .

Converse of the Corollary 3.3 is not true by the following Example.

Example 3.6. Let $S = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & r_1 & r_2 & r_3 \\ 0 & 0 & r_4 & r_5 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & r_6 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & r_7 \end{pmatrix} \mid r_i^s \text{ are real numbers} \right\}$.

Let $Q = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & x_1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & x_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & x_3 \end{pmatrix} \mid x_i^s \text{ are real numbers} \right\}$ is a quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal of S but Q is not a bi quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal of S by $[r'q \cap qr''q] \cap q = \phi$ and $[qr' \cap qr''q] \cap q = \phi$, where $q = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \in Q$ and $r' = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \in S$ and $r'' = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \in S$.

Theorem 3.4. *Every bi \mathcal{A} -ideal is a quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal.*

Proof. Suppose that B is a bi \mathcal{A} -ideal of S , B is a subsemiring of S and $BSB \cap B \neq \phi$. Now, $\phi \neq BSB \cap B \subseteq BS \cap B$ and $\phi \neq BSB \cap B \subseteq SB \cap B$. Thus, $\phi \neq BSB \cap B \subseteq [BS \cap SB] \cap B$. Hence B is a quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal of S .

Converse of the Theorem 3.4 may not be true by the following counter Example.

Example 3.7. The semiring S in Example 3.6,

$B = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & x_1 & x_2 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & x_3 \end{pmatrix} \mid x_i^s \text{ are are real numbers} \right\}$ is a subsemiring of S and

$SB = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & y_1 & y_2 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & y_3 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & y_4 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & y_5 \end{pmatrix} \mid y_i^s \text{ are are real numbers} \right\}$ and

$BS = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & z_1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & z_2 \end{pmatrix} \mid z_i^s \text{ are are real numbers} \right\}$.

Hence $[BS \cap SB] \cap B \neq \phi$. Thus, B is a quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal of S but B is not a bi \mathcal{A} -ideal of S by $br'b \cap b = \phi$, where $b = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \in B$ and $r' = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \in S$.

Theorem 3.5. *Every quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal is a \mathcal{A} -ideal.*

Proof. Suppose that Q is a quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal of S , then $[QS \cap SQ] \cap Q \neq \phi$. Now, $\phi \neq [QS \cap SQ] \cap Q \subseteq SQ \cap Q$ and $\phi \neq [QS \cap SQ] \cap Q \subseteq QS \cap Q$. Hence Q is a \mathcal{A} -ideal of S .

Converse of the Theorem 3.5 not true by the following Example.

Example 3.8. The semiring $S = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & r_1 & r_2 \\ 0 & 0 & r_3 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \mid r_i^s \text{ are real numbers} \right\}$ and

$Q = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & q_1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \mid q_1 \text{ is a real numbers} \right\}$ is a \mathcal{A} -ideal but Q is not a quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal of S by $[qr' \cap r''q] \cap q = \phi$, where $q = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \in Q$, $r' = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \in S$ and $r'' = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \in S$.

Theorem 3.6. *Every bi quasi ideal is a bi quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal.*

Proof. Suppose that Q is a bi quasi ideal of S , then $QS \cap QSQ \subseteq Q$ and $SQ \cap QSQ \subseteq Q$. Now, $[QS \cap QSQ] \cap Q \subseteq Q \cap Q \neq \phi$ and $[SQ \cap QSQ] \cap Q \subseteq Q \cap Q \neq \phi$. Hence Q is a bi quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal of S .

Converse of the Theorem 3.6 is not true as by the Example.

Example 3.9. The semiring S in Example 3.6,

$$Q = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & x_1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & x_2 & x_3 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & x_4 \end{pmatrix} \middle| x_i^s \text{ are real numbers} \right\} \text{ is a subsemiring of } S,$$

$$SQ = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & y_1 & y_2 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & y_3 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & y_4 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & y_5 \end{pmatrix} \middle| y_i^s \text{ are real numbers} \right\},$$

$$QS = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & z_1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & z_2 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & z_3 \end{pmatrix} \middle| z_i^s \text{ are real numbers} \right\} \text{ and}$$

$$QSQ = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & l_1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & l_2 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & l_3 \end{pmatrix} \middle| l_i^s \text{ are real numbers} \right\}. \text{ Thus, } [SQ \cap QSQ] \cap Q = [QS \cap QSQ] \cap Q$$

$$Q = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & u \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & v \end{pmatrix} \middle| u, v \text{ are real numbers} \right\} \neq \phi.$$

Hence Q is a bi quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal but Q is not a bi quasi ideal of S by $QS \cap QSQ = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & x \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & y \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & z \end{pmatrix} \middle| x, y, z \text{ are real numbers} \right\} \not\subseteq Q$.

Theorem 3.7. If Q is a \mathcal{A} -ideal (bi \mathcal{A} -ideal, quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal, bi quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal) of S and $Q \subseteq Q' \subseteq S$, then Q' is a \mathcal{A} -ideal (bi \mathcal{A} -ideal, quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal, bi quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal) of S .

Proof. Suppose that Q is a bi quasi \mathcal{A} ideal of S with $Q \subseteq Q' \subseteq S$. Then $\phi \neq [QS \cap QSQ] \cap Q \subseteq [Q'S \cap Q'SQ'] \cap Q'$ and $\phi \neq [SQ \cap QSQ] \cap Q \subseteq [SQ' \cap Q'SQ'] \cap Q'$. Therefore Q' is a bi quasi \mathcal{A} ideal of S .

Corollary 3.8. The union of \mathcal{A} -ideals (bi \mathcal{A} -ideals, quasi \mathcal{A} -ideals, bi quasi \mathcal{A} -ideals) of S is a \mathcal{A} -ideal (bi \mathcal{A} -ideal, quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal, bi quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal) of S .

Proof. Let I_1 and I_2 be any two \mathcal{A} -ideals of S . Then $I_1 \subseteq I_1 \cup I_2$, by Theorem 3.7, $I_1 \cup I_2$ is a \mathcal{A} -ideal of S .

4. VARIOUS TRI \mathcal{A} -IDEALS

Definition 4.1. Suppose that I and Q are non-empty subsets of a semiring $(S, +, \cdot)$. Then

- (i) I is called a right (left) tri ideal of S if I is a subsemiring of R and $I^2SI \subseteq I(ISI^2 \subseteq I)$.
- (ii) Q is called a right (left) tri quasi ideal of S if Q is a subsemiring of R and $QS \cap Q^2SQ \subseteq Q$ ($SQ \cap QSQ^2 \subseteq Q$).
- (iii) Q is called a tri quasi ideal of S if Q is a right tri quasi ideal and left tri quasi ideal of S .

Definition 4.2. Suppose that I and Q are non-empty subsets of a semiring $(S, +, \cdot)$. Then

- (i) I is called a right (left) tri \mathcal{A} -ideal of S if I is a subsemiring of S and $I^2SI \cap I \neq \phi$ ($ISI^2 \cap I \neq \phi$).
- (ii) I is called a tri \mathcal{A} -ideal of S if I is a right tri \mathcal{A} -ideal and left tri \mathcal{A} -ideal of S .
- (iii) Q is called a right (left) tri quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal of S if Q is a subsemiring of S and $[QS \cap Q^2SQ] \cap Q \neq \phi$ ($[SQ \cap QSQ^2] \cap Q \neq \phi$).
- (iv) Q is called a tri quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal of S if Q is a right tri quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal and left tri quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal of S .

Theorem 4.1. *Every ideal (bi ideal, quasi ideal, tri ideal) is a tri \mathcal{A} -ideal.*

Converse of the Theorem 4.1 may not true by the following Example.

Example 4.3. Let $S = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} \mid a, b, c, d \in \mathbb{Z}_2 \right\}$ as a semiring.

(i) The subsemiring $I_1 = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \right\}$ is a tri \mathcal{A} -ideal of S but I_1 is not an ideal of S by $I_1 S = S \not\subseteq I_1$ and $S I_1 = S \not\subseteq I_1$.

(ii) The subsemiring $B = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \right\}$ is a tri \mathcal{A} -ideal of S but B is not a bi ideal of S by $B S B = S \not\subseteq B$.

(iii) The subsemiring $Q = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \right\}$ is a tri \mathcal{A} -ideal of S but Q is not a quasi ideal of S by $Q S \cap S Q = S \not\subseteq Q$.

(iv) $I_2 = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \right\}$ is a tri \mathcal{A} -ideal of S but I_2 is not a tri ideal of S by $I_2^2 S I_2 \not\subseteq I_2$ and $I_2 S I_2^2 \not\subseteq I_2$ of S .

Theorem 4.2. *Every tri \mathcal{A} -ideal is a \mathcal{A} -ideal (bi \mathcal{A} -ideal).*

Proof. Suppose that I is a tri \mathcal{A} -ideal of S , then I is a subsemiring of S and $I^2 S I \cap I \neq \phi$ and $I S I^2 \cap I \neq \phi$. Now, $\phi \neq I^2 S I \cap I \subseteq I S I \cap I \subseteq I S \cap I$ and $\phi \neq I S I I \cap I \subseteq S I \cap I$. Hence I is a \mathcal{A} -ideal of S .

Converse of the Theorem 4.2 may not be true as in the given Example.

Example 4.4. (i) Let $S_1 = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & r_1 & r_2 & r_3 \\ 0 & 0 & r_4 & r_5 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & r_6 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \mid r_i^s \text{ are real numbers} \right\}$ is a semiring.

Let $I = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & i_1 & i_2 \\ 0 & 0 & i_3 & i_4 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & i_5 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \mid i_i^s \text{ are real numbers} \right\}$. Clearly I is a \mathcal{A} -ideal of S_1 but I is

not a tri \mathcal{A} -ideal of S_1 by $i^2 r i \cap i = \phi$ and $i r i^2 \cap i = \phi$, where $i = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \in I$ and

$r = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \in S_1$.

(ii) Let $S_2 = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & r_1 & r_2 & r_3 & r_4 & r_5 \\ 0 & 0 & r_6 & r_7 & r_8 & r_9 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & r_{10} & r_{11} & r_{12} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & r_{13} & r_{14} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & r_{15} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \mid r_i^s \text{ are real numbers} \right\}$ is a semiring.

Clearly $B = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & b_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & b_2 & b_3 & b_4 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & b_5 & b_6 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & b_7 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \mid b_i^s \text{ are real numbers} \right\}$ is a bi \mathcal{A} -ideal but B is not a

tri \mathcal{A} -ideal of S_2 by $b r b^2 \cap b = \phi$ and $b^2 r b \cap b = \phi$, where $b = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \in B$ and

$r = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \in S_2$.

Theorem 4.3. *Every tri \mathcal{A} -ideal is a quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal.*

Proof. Suppose that Q is a tri \mathcal{A} -ideal of S , then $Q^2SQ \cap Q \neq \phi$ and $QSQ^2 \cap Q \neq \phi$. Since Q is a subsemiring of S , $\phi \neq Q^2SQ \cap Q \subseteq QSQ \cap Q \subseteq QS \cap Q$ and $\phi \neq Q^2SQ \cap Q \subseteq QSQ \cap Q \subseteq SQ \cap Q$. Hence $\phi \neq Q^2SQ \cap Q \subseteq [QS \cap SQ] \cap Q$. Similarly, $\phi \neq QSQ^2 \cap Q \subseteq [QS \cap SQ] \cap Q$. Hence Q is a quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal of S .

Converse of the Theorem 4.3 may not be true in the given Example.

Example 4.5. The semiring S_2 in Example 4.4,

$$Q = \left\{ \left(\begin{array}{cccccc} 0 & 0 & 0 & q_1 & q_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & q_3 & q_4 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & q_5 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{array} \right) \middle| q_i \text{'s are real numbers} \right\}$$

is a quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal but Q is not a tri \mathcal{A} -ideal of S_2 by $q^2rq \cap q = \phi$ and $qrq^2 \cap q = \phi$, where $q = \left(\begin{array}{cccccc} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{array} \right) \in Q$ and

$$r = \left(\begin{array}{cccccc} 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{array} \right) \in S_2.$$

Corollary 4.4. *Every tri \mathcal{A} -ideal is a bi quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal.*

Proof. Suppose that Q is a right tri \mathcal{A} -ideal of S , then $Q^2SQ \cap Q \neq \phi$. Since Q is a subsemiring of S , $\phi \neq Q^2SQ \cap Q \subseteq QS \cap Q$ and $\phi \neq Q^2SQ \cap Q \subseteq QSQ \cap Q$. This implies that $\phi \neq Q^2SQ \cap Q \subseteq [QS \cap QSQ] \cap Q$. Thus, Q is a right bi quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal of S . Suppose that Q is a left tri \mathcal{A} -ideal of S , then Q is a left bi quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal of S . Hence, Q is a bi quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal of S .

Converse of the Corollary 4.4 may not be true in the given Example.

Example 4.6. Let $S = \left\{ \left(\begin{array}{cccc} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ r_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ r_2 & r_3 & 0 & 0 \\ r_4 & r_5 & r_6 & r_7 \end{array} \right) \middle| r_i \text{'s are real numbers} \right\}$ and

$$Q = \left\{ \left(\begin{array}{cccc} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ q_1 & q_2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & q_3 & 0 & q_4 \end{array} \right) \middle| q_i \text{'s are real numbers} \right\}$$

be subsemirings. Now, $SQ = \left\{ \left(\begin{array}{cccc} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ c_1 & c_2 & 0 & c_3 \end{array} \right) \middle| c_i \text{'s are real numbers} \right\}$ and

$$QS = \left\{ \left(\begin{array}{cccc} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ d_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ d_2 & d_3 & d_4 & d_5 \end{array} \right) \middle| d_i \text{'s are real numbers} \right\},$$

$$QSQ = \left\{ \left(\begin{array}{cccc} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ e_1 & e_2 & 0 & e_3 \end{array} \right) \middle| e_i \text{'s are real numbers} \right\}.$$

Thus, $[QS \cap QSQ] \cap Q \neq \phi$ and $[SQ \cap QSQ] \cap Q \neq \phi$. Hence Q is a bi quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal of S . But Q is not a tri \mathcal{A} -ideal of S by $q^2r'q \cap q = \phi$ and $qr'q^2 \cap q = \phi$, where

$$q = \left(\begin{array}{cccc} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 \end{array} \right) \in Q \text{ and } r' = \left(\begin{array}{cccc} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \end{array} \right) \in S.$$

Theorem 4.5. *Every bi quasi ideal is a tri quasi ideal.*

Proof. Suppose that Q is a bi quasi ideal of S then $SQ \cap QSQ \subseteq Q$ and $QS \cap QSQ \subseteq Q$. Now, $SQ \cap QSQ^2 \subseteq SQ \cap QSQ \subseteq Q$ and $QS \cap Q^2SQ \subseteq QS \cap QSQ \subseteq Q$, since Q is a subsemiring of S . Hence Q is a tri quasi ideal of S .

Converse of Theorem 4.5 not true by the following Example.

Example 4.7. The semiring S in Example 4.6,

$$Q = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ a_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & a_2 & 0 & a_3 \end{pmatrix} \middle| a_i^s \text{ are real numbers} \right\} \text{ is a subsemiring of } S.$$

$$\text{Now, } SQ = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ c_1 & c_2 & 0 & c_3 \end{pmatrix} \middle| c_i^s \text{ are real numbers} \right\},$$

$$QS = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ d_1 & d_2 & d_3 & d_4 \end{pmatrix} \middle| d_i^s \text{ are real numbers} \right\},$$

$$QSQ = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ e_1 & e_2 & 0 & e_3 \end{pmatrix} \middle| e_i^s \text{ are real numbers} \right\} \text{ and}$$

$$QSQ^2 = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & f_1 & 0 & f_2 \end{pmatrix} \middle| f_i^s \text{ are real numbers} \right\}. \text{ Thus, } SQ \cap QSQ^2 \subseteq Q. \text{ Hence}$$

$$Q \text{ is a tri quasi ideal of } S \text{ but } Q \text{ is not a left bi quasi ideal of } S \text{ by } SQ \cap QSQ = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ h_1 & h_2 & 0 & h_3 \end{pmatrix} \middle| h_i^s \text{ are real numbers} \right\} \not\subseteq Q.$$

Corollary 4.6. Every tri quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal is a bi quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal.

Proof. Suppose that Q is a tri quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal of S then $[QS \cap Q^2SQ] \cap Q \neq \phi$ and $[SQ \cap QSQ^2] \cap Q \neq \phi$. Since Q is a subsemiring of S , $\phi \neq [QS \cap Q^2SQ] \cap Q \subseteq [QS \cap QSQ] \cap Q$ and $\phi \neq [SQ \cap QSQ^2] \cap Q \subseteq [SQ \cap QSQ] \cap Q$. Hence Q is a bi quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal of S .

Converse of the Corollary 4.6 is not true in the following Example.

Example 4.8. The semiring S in Example 4.6,

$$Q = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ a_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & a_2 & 0 & a_3 \end{pmatrix} \middle| a_i^s \text{ are real numbers} \right\} \text{ is a bi quasi } \mathcal{A}\text{-ideal of } S \text{ but } Q \text{ is not}$$

a tri quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal of S by $[r'q \cap qr''q^2] \cap q = \phi$ and $[qr' \cap q^2r''q] \cap q = \phi$, where

$$q = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \in Q \text{ and } r' = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \in S \text{ and } r'' = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \in S.$$

Theorem 4.7. If Q is a tri \mathcal{A} -ideal (tri quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal) of S and $Q \subseteq Q' \subseteq S$, then Q' is a tri \mathcal{A} -ideal (tri quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal) of S .

Proof. Suppose that Q is a tri quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal of S with $Q \subseteq Q' \subseteq S$. Then $\phi \neq [QS \cap QSQ^2] \cap Q \subseteq [Q'S \cap Q'SQ'^2] \cap Q'$ and $\phi \neq [SQ \cap Q^2SQ] \cap Q \subseteq [SQ' \cap Q'^2SQ'] \cap Q'$. Therefore, Q' is a tri quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal of S .

Corollary 4.8. The union of tri \mathcal{A} -ideals (tri quasi \mathcal{A} -ideals) of S is a tri \mathcal{A} -ideal (tri quasi \mathcal{A} -ideal) of S .

Proof. Let Q_1 and Q_2 be any two tri \mathcal{A} -ideals of S . Then $Q_1 \subseteq Q_1 \cup Q_2$, by Theorem 4.7, $Q_1 \cup Q_2$ is a tri \mathcal{A} -ideal of S .

5. CONCLUSIONS

The main goal of this work is to present a various ideals and \mathcal{A} -ideals in semirings. So in future, we should consider the various generalized ideals and generalized \mathcal{A} -ideals in semirings.

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M. PALANIKUMAR

ANNAMALAI UNIVERSITY, DEPARTMENT OF MATHEMATICS, CHIDAMBARAM, 608002, INDIA
Email address: palanimaths86@gmail.com

K. ARULMOZHI

ANNAMALAI UNIVERSITY, DEPARTMENT OF MATHEMATICS, CHIDAMBARAM, 608002, INDIA
Email address: arulmozhiems@gmail.com